

OrganKits project

OrganKits partners have been working on the project and have several updates to share!

The main activities of our project are presented in this 4th newsletter.

Want to find more?

Contact us or visit our website

Top stories

Schools Across Europe Invited to Join the OrganKits

The OrganKits Project is reaching out to secondary schools across Europe to participate in a special Meeting with Associated Schools.

[Read more...](#)

Breaking Ground in Education

Duca Abruzzi School is revolutionizing the educational landscape with bold initiatives designed to inspire, innovate, and expand learning opportunities for students across the region.

[Read more...](#)

The Organ Kits project celebrates the Erasmus days

On October 15th, the Erasmus Days live event brought science, education, and innovation to life offering participants a first-hand look at the groundbreaking OrganKits project.

[Read more...](#)

The second implementation cycle

Our project has reached a milestone, with all participating schools and organizations receiving their new shipment of plastinated anatomical kits for the 2024/2025 academic year.

[See more](#)

